

a very distressing sense of numbness and tingling, with coldness of the extremities, so severe that she was at times quite unable to walk, and, as she expressed it, "they felt as if they did not belong to her;" pulse 99, and very feeble. She did not complain of *actual pain* in any part. I now ascertained that she had taken some camphor dissolved in rectified spirit of wine and tincture of myrrh; and I have since found that the quantity of camphor taken must have been about a scruple, an extremely small dose to produce such violent symptoms. It was taken for a pain in the back, and was followed by a cup of tea in about half an hour, when the above-named symptoms immediately supervened.

Vomiting not being induced by tickling the fauces with a feather, I gave her a scruple of sulphate of zinc, and sent for a stomach-pump, but before it arrived copious vomiting had been produced, of a yellowish liquid, smelling strongly of camphor. I now gave her some gum arabic, dissolved in water. The vomiting subsided, and she appeared somewhat relieved; but as the last portion of the fluid ejected from the stomach still emitted a powerful odour of camphor, I gave her ten grains more of sulphate of zinc. It soon produced the desired effect; and, as the sickness continued for some time, the smell of camphor at length became almost imperceptible, and she appeared to be much relieved, the breathing being less difficult, and at times almost natural, but the sensations in the limbs continued nearly the same. I directed that her legs should be kept in hot water for twenty minutes, and then wrapped in warm flannel, and the patient put to bed, and to take a mixture of opium and ether, in small doses, with compound tragacanth powder, every three hours, and a mustard poultice to be applied over the stomach.

In the evening I found her greatly relieved; the breathing tranquil, pulse 80, and all the other symptoms less violent; but I was informed that the dyspnoea, accompanied with dimness of sight, had returned several times during the day; and there was also considerable tenderness at the epigastrium, which I chiefly ascribed to the vomiting. On the following morning I was sent for in haste, the dyspnoea having returned, and the patient was reported to have had several slight convulsive fits during the night. I found her with a frequent pulse (about 100), but yielding readily to pressure; a dry tongue, and somewhat furred; complaining of much tenderness at the epigastric region on pressure, and the bowels constipated. I ordered a blister to the epigastrium, and a laxative draught to be taken immediately; and after the bowels had been freely moved, a mixture of liquor of the acetate of ammonia with ipecacuanha wine, and the sedative liquor of opium, to be repeated every four hours.

On the following day I found that the draught had acted well, and the blister also, and she was altogether much better; and from this time had no serious relapse, although for some weeks she had occasional attacks of dyspnoea, generally lasting only a few minutes. She has now enjoyed her usual health for many months past. I am, Sir,

CHAS. HALLETT, M.R.C.S.L. & L.A.C.
Axminster, Sept. 21, 1842.

POTATOES AS A PREVENTIVE OF SEA-SCURVY.

To the Editor of THE LANCET.

SIR,—In your valuable Periodical of the 3rd inst., I noticed a few remarks by Mr. Dalton on the efficacy of potatoes as a preventive of sea-scurvy, I have myself, also, observed the beneficial results of their use, in situations where that disease was likely to prevail. The subject has hitherto not been made sufficiently public for the welfare of persons exposed to long voyages. During a passage of four months, to Van Dieman's Land, and one of four months back, a sufficient quantity of potatoes was laid in, to allow of some being served out to all hands daily, and not one symptom of scurvy appeared, amongst either the crew or the emigrants, although living on salt provisions the whole time.

The captains of many French and American whalers, lying in Hobart Town, assured me that they never knew the scurvy to appear in their ships, so long as they could obtain potatoes for the crews; and they always made a point of laying in a good stock, when refitting, or calling at any of the Australasian ports, where that vegetable grows most plentifully. I consider it decidedly superior to lime-juice, which is apt to cause acidity, flatulence, and various gastric disorders, as I experienced amply on board the *Tasmania*, where all who had taken it, even when mixed with brandy and sugar, were more or less indisposed. The potatoes we brought from Hobart Town, after a four months' voyage round Cape Horn, and through the tropical climates, were still as fresh, on arriving in the river, as when we left. They were merely packed in large hampers, well closed, and not exposed to the air. I do not believe it necessary that they should be eaten raw, or with vinegar, but boiled in the usual way. I had an opportunity of seeing, in Van Dieman's Land, a convict ship arrive, with about four hundred men, after a five months' passage. Amongst them were between thirty and forty cases of scurvy, some very severe. Many of the persons died as soon as brought on shore. Now lime-juice was used freely in that ship; but had she touched at the Cape, and taken in a fresh supply of potatoes, the fearful ravages

that I witnessed would most undoubtedly have been prevented, and many lives saved. Another instance of sea-scurvy I saw on board the *Mississippi*, a French whaler, that had been eight months on the whaling-grounds, without touching at any port. The result was, that on their arrival in Hobart Town, every man in the ship was more or less affected: they had had lime-juice, but no potatoes. I attended the crew until they got well, and advised the captain to lay in a stock of them; to which he readily consented. Of course, it must be understood, all along, that strict regard be paid at the same time to cleanliness and ventilation, without which fresh provisions of any kind would be of little avail, in crowded ships, on long voyages. I have the honour to remain, Sir, your most obedient servant,

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late Surgeon to the ship *Tasmania*.
Dover-road, Borough,
Sept. 19, 1842.

LIGATURES.—ANEURISMS.

THE ligature is alone to be trusted in bleeding from divided arteries; it is the easiest, the least painful, the most effectual mode. It mechanically stops the hæmorrhage; it also stimulates the living vessels to reaction, and excites their adhesion and final obliteration—a double office. At the time when writers on surgery imagined that the ligature brought the inner coats of an artery into the state of an incised wound, I foresaw what follies would be committed, and proved to the large class of intelligent students I then had, that by placing a circular ligature around the artery, letting it lie in contact with the proper coat of the artery, without *drawing it at all*, the artery stopped by a clot. It is not necessary to draw the ligature so as to cut the inner coats, and it is not safe, unless in young and healthy subjects, and in amputations. The mode in which a ligature should be employed in old arteries that are subject to aneurism forms an important consideration. It is very dangerous to apply the experience acquired in employing ligatures in operations on the healthy subject, to the subject of aneurisms. Far less is it safe to conclude from experiments on brutes. In Dr. Jones's experiments I foresaw that surgeons would be nicking the coats of an artery, by applying a ligature and taking it off again. It did not succeed in the very best hands. Mr. Travers has written some ingenious papers on the temporary ligature in the case of aneurisms; but he has *peculiar merit in resigning the use of it*. Asalini and Sir P. Crampton have simply compressed the artery for a time sufficient to form a clot; but I advise you to employ the ligature as I have described it. In ligatures, one folly has been the substi-

tion of catgut for the common thread, supposing that from its being an animal substance it would be absorbed. It does dissolve and get loose, and abscesses form where it lies. Use a ligature of two or four threads, according to the size of the artery. Take care in preparing it that the threads are laid parallel, and waxed and oiled before application. Tie with a simple knot, and tie it again. Be sure, where the case is of importance, that the ligature is in contact with the coats of the artery,—that neither fascia nor fat, nor even the sheath, intervene. Do not cut off the ends of the ligature, but twist them together into the smallest compass, and lay them down on the side of the wound; and if there be many ligatures arrange them, and mark the one that is on the principal artery by knotting it. The common error is, that of including a portion of cellular membrane and sheath, and then the vessel not being in contact with the ligature does not inflame, and the substance so included wasting, the mouth of it is open. Mr. Lawrence is the advocate of small, hard, single thread-ligatures, which he cuts off short by the knot. This (John Bell's practice) I do not approve. The object is to procure immediate adhesion, which it is alleged is prevented by the common manner of retaining the ends of ligatures. I have seen patients shrieking and complaining of their toes where ligatures were put on the arteries on the face of the stump. In fact, the ligature often includes the nerve. Conceive the painful misfortune of a fine, hard thread tied on a nerve, and the ends cut off, and you will not follow this fashion, for it is but a fashion. Long after the stump should have been well ulcerations have existed, from the ligatures being cut short, and the noose left. Some writers do not seem to know the practical advantages of a tolerably thick ligature, both ends being permitted to remain. When these ligatures are to be taken away, nothing is more easy. The ends are twisted, the noose is tightened. If the ligature come not away, fasten the ends thus twisted up the side of the wound, and at the next dressing a further twist brings them away. Just before I left London the following occurred to a hospital surgeon. On going his round he was ashamed of a stump that was kept open by a ligature hanging from it; so, that it should no longer offend him, he took hold of the cord and violently pulled it away, when a jet of blood came full from the femoral artery. If what I have above recommended be not done, the surgeon is obliged to tug directly on the end of the vessel, and he may disturb the coagululum. The same happens when the surgeon cuts away one end of the ligature, for then what remains cannot be twisted. If the ligature be not twisted, and the threads lie loose, they get entangled in the granulations.—*Lectures of Sir Charles Bell at Edinburgh.*